

WAYS OF EFFECTIVE USE OF MODERN METHODS AND TOOLS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

In this article, special attention has been paid to the development of agriculture in our country in recent years, the lack of a long-term strategy for the development of agriculture, the timely implementation of a number of measures specified in the Strategy, the livelihood of the population. a new stage ensuring the well-being and others will be briefly discussed.

Agriculture—One of the measures taken after the April Revolution was a decree to cancel the debts owed to the landlords and landowners by the landless and landless peasants. He implemented the government program taking into account the participation of hard-working farmers in land reform. In the organization of agricultural cooperatives, it is planned to attract landless and landless farmers, nomadic poor.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the development of agriculture in our country. In particular, the adoption of the strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 is of great importance in the radical reform of the sector.

Consequently, as a result of the implementation of the priority tasks defined in the Strategy, new economic entities were launched. Modern methods and advanced forms of economic management, including clusters of various specializations, agricultural associations (cooperatives) were established. At the same time, a total of 51,900 hectares of land was put back into use in the regions.

However, along with these achievements, there are also problems affecting the timely and effective implementation of a number of activities defined in the Strategy. In particular, the principles of public-private partnership in land development have not been properly implemented, and problems related to private investment in the sector have not been fully resolved. Contractual relations between farms growing cotton raw materials and cotton-textile clusters are not properly established.

According to the decree "ON THE APPROVAL OF THE AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN FOR 2020 — 2030" in the following years, the reform of our country's agriculture, in particular, the improvement of the state management system in the field, the wide current market relations certain works are

being carried out in order to strengthen the legal basis of relations between the entities that grow, process and sell agricultural products, attract investments to the sector, introduce resource-saving technologies and provide agricultural products producers with modern techniques .

At the same time, the absence of a long-term strategy for the development of agriculture hinders the effective use of land and water resources, the widespread attraction of investments in the sector, the high income of producers and the increase of competitiveness of products.

It is known that the strategy of the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 was adopted by the decree of the head of our country on October 23 of this year. Within the framework of this document, the modernization of the industry was started based on a modern approach. Also, on November 7, the President's decision "On measures for rapid development of livestock industries in the Republic of Karakalpakstan" was adopted.

All over the world, silage and silage are mainly used for livestock feeding. When 50-60 tons of silage per hectare were obtained from the intensive variety of corn as a repeated crop in Yangiyol district, the cost of 1 kilogram of it was only 150 soums. However, the market price of 1 kg of shelukha exceeds 2,000 soums. That is, livestock farmers can easily grow fodder 10 times cheaper than shrot-shelukha.

It is possible to get up to 100 quintals per hectare from fodder wheat. However, instead of taking measures to compensate for the deficit of food and fodder in places, the cases of inefficient and purposeless use of nutritious cropland were criticized.

In Uzbekistan, agricultural modernization processes serve as one of the important tools of the economy in the strategic plans promoted by our state.

These strategic plans are a new stage of ensuring the well-being of the population. New technologies also play a role in the development of the agricultural sector. Efforts to provide agriculture with modern technologies are rapidly progressing in the country. In general, in recent years, the state has paid great attention to the radical reform of the agrarian sector and its adaptation to market requirements.

It should be noted that in 2021, a number of normative documents on the development of agriculture were adopted. In particular, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the further development of the system of knowledge and innovations in agriculture and the provision of modern services” and “Knowledge in agriculture under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and “On the organization of the activities of the national innovation center” was adopted. “The concept of priority development of the system of knowledge and innovations in agriculture in 2021-2025” was approved by the above decree.

The development of agriculture is one of the important factors in directly ensuring the well-being of the population. Since this industry is the leading “driver” of the country’s economy, the acceleration of many modernization works in the industry is one of the important tasks of today. Therefore, in recent years, strategies for the development of agriculture have been developed and are being implemented in the country. This is an important process to ensure the well-being of the people. After all, the efforts being made in the development of this sector serve to increase the income of peasants and farmers in the country, create new jobs, and increase productivity.

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